

Transforming Banking Sector through Artificial Intelligence

Prof. Neelima B Nimbhorkar

Principal, Adarsha Vidya Kendra College, Bengaluru

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:
Nimbhorkar, Neelima B.
“Transforming Banking Sector through Artificial Intelligence.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 215–18.

DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1403619>

Abstract

Today, majority banks are eyeing towards Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology to help them use huge volume of data to increase customer engagement, to improve compliance and operational efficiency. Increased use of Artificial Intelligence in banking sector is showing a signs of interest and adoption as a result, all most all of the Indian banking sectors have started AI adoption. Its application in data analysis and customer service is creating an opportunity to become more personalized towards its customers through better insights and automation of backend work flows. The concept of AI is to stimulate the intelligence of human beings into machines with the help of sophisticated machine learning language and natural language processing algorithms, so that humans and AI will work together. AI will create growth through improved customer and employee experiences. In short, AI will enable to move away from repetitive tasks to more strategic and innovative kinds of work.

Keywords: Operational efficiency, Artificial Intelligence, Sophisticated machine, learning language, Processing algorithm, Data analysis.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence has been around since 1956. Artificial Intelligence is the development of computer systems which enable to perform tasks that would require human intelligence. Recent developments in AI meant that AI powered applications became commercially viable. Artificial intelligence can be defined as “an ideal intelligent machine which is a flexible rational agent capable of perceiving its environment and takeremedial actions.AI is a group of related technologies which includes big data analytics, machine learning, deep learning, predictive analytics, and natural language. Artificial intelligence enablesthe banking companies to reformulate their work by creating innovative products and services, and transforming customer experiences.

Objectives

- To understand the concept of Artificial intelligence.
- To analyze importance and applicability of AI in banking sector.
- To evaluate the feasibility of using AI to transform the banking sector.

Literature Review

In recent years, Artificial Intelligence has impacted the Banking industry. It's a challenge for the banking industry, to keep up with competition, and standing themselves as an innovative company in the market. Artificial Intelligence is a banking tool that helps the banking sectors to manage their business through effective planning and developing the services. Banks may use artificial intelligence for enhancing a business strategy to determine how it can be used for its efficient functioning and uninterrupted service provisions to its customer.

Methodology of the Study

Today artificial intelligence has become priority issue today for banking sector. Rapid advances in AI are coming at a time of widespread technological and digital disruption. It will bring completely new opportunities for the workforce – in the form of new jobs and new skill sets, hence it is necessary to know how the AI plays role in transforming the banking sector. The study is based on the conceptual framework and secondary source of data collection is being used to elaborate research objectives.

Definitions of Artificial Intelligence

John McCarthy defined it as “the science and engineering of making intelligent machines”. It is a consummate “intelligent” machine that is a supple rational agent capable of perceiving its environment and takes measures that increase its probability of success. It is the blend of three advanced technologies – machine learning, natural language processing and cognitive computing.

Relevance and applicability of Artificial Intelligence in Banking sector

- Today computers can handle most of the customer service queries due to matured speech processing and natural language processing technologies. This would mark an end to waiting in line results in customer satisfaction.
- Bank to customer personal connect will see drastic growth through AI, as automated financial services can be made possible to provide which generates expertise in making financial decisions. Even banks can analyze market behavior for setting the financial goals and personal portfolio.
- As humans and AI start to work together, banks will really feel the benefits of AI in cost reduction and revenue growth which may results in increased development of state-of-the-art products and enhancement in income per product, volume, customer retention and acquisition.
- With the help of AI and machine learning, financial marketers are being challenged to connect activity and behavioural inputs like transaction history, website inquiries, and social media interactions with consumer-centric outputs.
- Chat bots seems to be the primary AI used at Indian banks today through conversational app for focussing on customer service. This helps to address several queries, assimilate knowledge from various sources and improves accuracy rate.
- Today AI also helps banking sector to innovate its services, accordingly several apps have been introduced to answer FAQs and get in touch with the bank for loan & other products.
- AI assists to boost the most relevant products and services in email, thus streamlining the online process.
- Fraud detection has become one of the important fields to boost accurate and superior results with the intervention of artificial intelligence.

Feasibility of using AI to transform the banking sector

- Machine learning helps to direct consumers to the right messages and locations on the website as well as to generate outbound personalized content.
- Anti-money laundering (AML) has been designed to stop the practice of generating income through illegal actions.
- Plenty of Hedge funds across the globe are using high artificial intelligence models to extract or pool the funds from several sources of financial markets by allowing the investors to take a right investment decision.
- HDFC Bank has developed an AI-based chat bot, “Eva”, to address the customer queries and accordingly bank interacted with over 530,000 unique users, and held 1.2 million conversations. Even bank is collecting the knowledge from thousands of sources to provide solutions in less than 0.4 seconds. Within the first few days of its launch, Eva has answered several queries from thousands of customers across the globe.
- ICICI Bank launched its AI-based chat bot, named iPal to interact with the millions of its customers and answered several queries with a 90% accuracy rate.
- Even Axis Bank launched an innovation lab called “Thought Factory” to accelerate the development of innovative AI technology solutions. They developed AI & NLP (Natural Language Processing) enabled app for Conversational Banking which helped its consumers for financial and non-financial matters related issues.
- Several applications of machine learning enable customer service, personal, financial/ wealth management, and fraud/risk management.
- Impact of machine learning’s can be seen everywhere in the front, middle or back office in the form of lesser errors, prompt decisions, greater efficiency and customer experience.
- Today Deep Learning is getting used as a subset of machine learning to detect frauds PayPal is a very good example to fight against fraud.
- Deep learning is also useful in finding out new business opportunities. It also helps bank to understand the customer behaviour to identify opportunities from their likes and preferences.

Benefits of using AI in Banking

- **Saves cost:** As AI helps in providing the qualitative banking services hence it can directly interact with its customers which helps in saving the costs.
- **Talent mapping:** AI helps in understanding the ability of the customers; accordingly banks can develop its products and services.
- **Saves time:** AI tools helps bank customers to arrive at proper investment decisions as these tools performs repetitive task and ultimately saves the time.
- **Productive work:** As AI provides the qualitative services which helps to improve productivity with maximum efficiency.
- **Quality services:** AI is supporting banks through several languages, chat bots and apps to generate quality products and services.

Conclusions

- Several banks have attained 100% accuracy in account-closure validations.
- It is observed remarkable improvements in processing time.
- AI results in better customer interaction through chat bots.
- Machine learning algorithms helping in fraud detection.
- AI is helping banks to create goodwill in the market.

References

15 Applications of AI and Machine Learning in Financial Marketing - By Jim Marous, Co-Publisher of the Financial Brand and Owner/Publisher of the Digital Banking Report.

A blog on 5 AI applications in banking to look out for in next 5 years.

AI in Banking – An Analysis of America’s 7 Top Banks - by Kumba Sennaar.

Artificial Intelligence Powered Banking – Infosys Finacle.